

Explainable EEG Transformer with Stacking Ensemble for classifying Dementia

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Abstract

Early and reliable detection of dementia remains a major clinical challenge, with electroencephalography (EEG) offering a promising non-invasive approach for real-world screening. In this study, we present a stacking ensemble framework in which a transformer-based meta-classifier integrates outputs from multiple base-learners including random forest, XGBoost, support vector machine, and logistic regression with a set of carefully selected EEG features. EEG recordings were obtained from 72 quantitative indices measured using a wearable 2-channel device. Feature selection was conducted within the cross-validation loop via ANOVA F-test to prevent information leakage, and the ten most stable features across folds were retained as meta-inputs. Across repeated cross-validation, the proposed meta-transformer achieved the highest balanced accuracy (0.694 ± 0.069), demonstrating both competitive performance and consistency. SHAP analysis revealed that the model drew on both base-learner probabilities and original EEG features, with Cog1, Cog2, and CohMaxF ranking among the most influential predictors. When restricted to EEG features alone, cognitive indices and coherence-based measures remained dominant contributors. These findings suggest that transformer-based stacking can effectively capture complex interactions between heterogeneous inputs, offering both accuracy and interpretability in EEG-based dementia classification.

Key words: Dementia, EEG, Transformer, Stacking Ensemble

Introduction

Dementia is a progressive neurodegenerative condition characterized by declines in memory, reasoning, and decision-making [1]. With an aging global population, the demand for early and reliable diagnostic tools has become increasingly urgent [2, 3]. Among various modalities, wearable and non-invasive electroencephalography (EEG) has emerged as a promising candidate for monitoring cognitive decline in real-world environments [4-6].

In recent years, ensemble learning has shown strong performance in biomedical signal classification, particularly for its robustness and ability to combine diverse model outputs [7, 8]. Stacking ensemble offers flexibility by allowing multiple base models to contribute to a higher-level decision through a meta-classifier [9-12]. However, traditional meta-models including logistic regression (LR), random forests (RF), support vector machine (SVM), and extreme gradient boosting (XGB) often rely on fixed, shallow architectures [12-16]. In addition, multi-layer perceptron (MLP) is constrained by their relatively static structure and lack of mechanisms for modeling contextual dependencies between base predictions [17, 18]. These approaches typically aggregate base model predictions by a simple linear combination, limiting their ability to capture complex interactions among features.

To address this limitation, we explore a transformer-based meta-classifier that operates within a stacking ensemble. By leveraging self-attention mechanisms [19], the model can dynamically assess relationships among predictions of base models and selected features, allowing for more expressive modeling of interactions and hierarchical patterns that are otherwise unrecognized by conventional meta-models.

This study investigates how transformer-based models can serve as effective meta-classifiers in stacking ensembles for EEG-based dementia classification. We aim to identify whether self-attention can better learn interdependencies between features and base model outputs in data-constrained, imbalanced settings. In addition to reproducing performance, we focus on model interpretability, using attention maps and Shapley additive explanations

(SHAP)[20] values to trace how different input features contribute to classification decisions.

Materials and Method

Participants

Forty-seven (12 males, 35 females) patients with dementia and 55 (26 males, 29 females) with mild cognitive impairment (MCI) were enrolled. Forty-three (16 males, 27 females) healthy controls (HCs) were recruited from the general medicine departments of the same hospital. All participants underwent brain MRI and the Seoul Neuropsychological Screening Battery. The Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) and Clinical Dementia Rating (CDR) were administered to all participants. Patients with dementia were included if they had deficits in cognitive domains including memory, executive function, and attention. Patients with MCI had mild impairments in memory, executive function, attention, and general cognition. All participants were excluded if they had psychiatric disorders or were taking psychiatric medications, had a history of traumatic brain injury, or had neurovascular disease. Patients with dementia with Lewy bodies, Parkinson's disease dementia, frontotemporal dementia, or rapidly progressive dementia (within two years) were also excluded. The mean ages of the dementia, MCI, and HC groups were 77.98 (7.14), 64.38 (7.49), and 59.40 (6.09) years, respectively. The mean years of formal education were 6.19 (4.26), 10.29 (3.68), and 12.95 (2.95), respectively. Patients with dementia had MMSE \leq 23 and CDR \geq 1. Patients with MCI had MMSE 24–27 and CDR 0.5. HCs had MMSE \geq 28 and CDR 0.

EEG recordings and preprocessing

Seated comfortably in a soundproof room, participants were asked to keep suppressing eye movements and remain still and silent. Resting state EEG recording was conducted for 160 s using Neuroharmony, a wearable 2-channel EEG device (PANAXTOS Co. Ltd, Seoul,

South Korea). Baseline signals were measured first 40 s with eyes open. Then, eyes closed with 60 s and those open with 40 s were recorded. Dry electrodes coated with gold were located on forehead sites at fp1 and fp2. The electrode on left ear lobe was referenced and central area (fpz) of forehead was grounded. The recording was sampled at 250 Hz. To remove physiological artifacts such as eye-movements, a 3-Hz high-pass was filtered for recording.

Quantitative EEG analysis

The eyes-closed and eyes-open (o) data were epoched into 40 segments each. All data were decomposed into frequency bands using the fast Fourier transform (FFT). Absolute and relative (r) band power were extracted for theta (T, 4.0–7.9 Hz), alpha (A, 8.0–12.9 Hz), sensorimotor rhythm (SMR, 13.0–15.9 Hz), low beta (BL, 13.0–20.9 Hz), and high beta (BH, 21.0–30.9 Hz). Left and right electrodes were numbered 1 and 2, respectively. We analyzed the following quantitative indices: cog, midF, rawRMS, avr, Fp, Fpv, FpCoh, Fs, Fsv, FsCoh, Corl, CohMaxF, CohMax, CohAvr, CohA_T, CohA_BL, CohT, CohA, CohBL, CohBH, A_T, T_S, T_BL, A_BL, A_BH, T, A, BL, BH, Tr, Ar, BLr, BHr, To, Ao, BLo, BHo, Tor, Aor, BLor, and BHor (Table 1).

Statistica analysis

Distributional differences in sex across groups were assessed using Pearson's chi-squared test. Demographic and clinical variables were compared across groups. Group differences in the 72 EEG indices were evaluated using multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA). All statistical tests were two-tailed with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$. Post hoc comparisons were performed using Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) test. To account for multiple testing across features, p-values were adjusted using the false discovery rate (FDR).

Proposed Framework

We propose a leakage-free, reproducible meta-learning framework to compare various meta-classifiers, including a transformer-based model, on tabular EEG data. The dataset was first divided into training and test sets using stratified sampling (8:2) to preserve the original class distribution. To address class imbalance in the training set, the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE)[21] was applied following standard feature scaling. Within the training set, validation was performed exclusively via repeated stratified cross-validation (5 folds * 10 repeats). To prevent data leakage, feature selection using the ANOVA F-test (SelectKBest) was conducted independently within each fold, ensuring that feature importance was computed solely from the training portion of the fold. Our framework consists of four main stages: (1) Feature selection with cross-validation, (2) Base-learner training and meta-feature generation, (3) Meta-model training using the stacked features, and (4) Model evaluation and interpretability via attention analysis and SHAP. We leverage stacking, a two-level ensemble approach, in which diverse base learners generate intermediate predictions. These are then concatenated with selected raw features to form the meta-inputs used by the meta-classifier. To ensure reliable and unbiased model comparison, all evaluations were conducted under a unified cross-validation protocol with strict control for information leakage.

Base-Learner

Given the original input data $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$ and corresponding labels $y \in \{0, 1, \dots, C-1\}^n$, we train a set of base learners: $M_{base} = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_k\}$, where $f_k: \mathbb{R}^{d'} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^c$. Specifically, we employ four base learners: RF, XGB, SVM, and LR. Each base model f_k outputs either a class label or a probability vector. These outputs are concatenated to form the meta-input $Z = [f_1(X'), f_2(X'), \dots, f_k(X'), X']$. Here, d' denotes the number of selected features, and C is the number of classes. Here, X' denotes the selected features after applying SelectKBest.

Meta-Learner

Once the meta-input matrix $Z \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, where $m = K \cdot C + d'$, is constructed from the outputs of the base learners and the selected features, the meta-learner is trained to map each sample $z_i \in \mathbb{R}^m$ to a final prediction. We compared the proposed transformer-based meta-classifier with conventional models (LR, SVM, RF, XGB, and MLP). All compared meta-models, except for the transformer-based model, were implemented using scikit-learn and XGBoost, with default hyperparameters unless otherwise stated. The proposed meta-learner is a lightweight transformer-based classifier built to capture complex interactions among base-learner outputs and selected features.

Each meta-input vector $z_i \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is first projected into a higher-dimensional embedding space: $h_f^{(0)} = z_i W_e + b_e$, $W_e \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times d_{\text{model}}}$

The embedded vector $h_f^{(0)}$ is passed through L stacked transformer encoder layers, each composed of multi-head self-attention and position-wise feed-forward sublayers: $H^{(l)} = \text{TransformerEncoder}^{(l)}(H^{(l-1)})$, $l = 1, \dots, L$

The output from the final encoder layer is used to predict class probabilities via a softmax classifier: $y^{\wedge}_i = \text{softmax}(W_c h_f^{(L)} + b_c)$, $W_c \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times d_{\text{model}}}$

The model is trained using cross-entropy loss: $L = -y_{1,1} \log(y^{\wedge}_{1,1}) + y_{1,2} \log(y^{\wedge}_{1,2}) + \dots + y_{n,C} \log(y^{\wedge}_{n,C})$

Evaluation

To rigorously evaluate the performance of each meta-classifier, we conducted 5-fold stratified cross-validation with 10 repeats on the training set. In each fold, feature selection was re-applied to prevent data leakage, ensuring that feature importance was evaluated independently of validation data. For each split, we retrained the base learners, generated meta-inputs, and trained the corresponding meta-model. Following the cross-validation phase, we retrained each meta-classifier on the entire training set using the same pipeline, and evaluated final performance on a held-out test set. Evaluation metrics included balanced

accuracy, macro-averaged precision, and F1-score, in order to fairly assess model performance under class imbalance.

Interpretability

For the proposed transformer-based meta-classifier, we further explored interpretability. We extracted attention weights from the final transformer encoder layer to understand which base learner outputs or raw features contributed most to each decision. We also applied SHAP using a permutation explainer adapted for the PyTorch model. SHAP values were computed for the meta-inputs, allowing us to identify and visualize the top 10 contributing features per prediction in the mixed view (base-learner outputs + original features), consistent with the number of features selected in the stability analysis. In addition, SHAP analysis was performed separately for original features only, where the top 10 features were reported.

Results

Demographic and clinical statistics are presented in Table 2. Significant differences were found among the groups in age, education, MMSE, and CDR. The mean age was highest and the level of formal education was lowest in patients with dementia. The difference in sex between groups was not significant. Patients with dementia showed the lowest MMSE score and the highest CDR score.

Significant differences in EEG features were found (Table 3). Patients with dementia showed a lower score in the Cog1 variable compared to those with MCI and HCs. In Cog2, there was a significant increase in scores, with dementia < MCI < HCs. In T_S1, patients with dementia had a higher value than those with MCI. Patients with dementia also showed a higher T_B1 score compared to MCI.

In the meta-model comparison, proposed meta-transformer achieved the best-balanced accuracy (0.69 ± 0.069), precision (0.687 ± 0.101), and F1 score (0.673 ± 0.085) (Table 4). Figure 2 shows the performance distribution from 50 runs of repeated cross-validation, where the median, mean, variability, and outliers can be visually compared across models. In each boxplot, the box spans the interquartile range (IQR) between the first (Q1) and third (Q3) quartiles, with the horizontal orange line indicating the median and the green triangle marking the mean. Whiskers extend to the most extreme values within $1.5 * IQR$ from the quartiles, while open circles represent outliers beyond this range. Figure 3 illustrates the achievable performance range for each meta-model. Table 4 presents the corresponding numerical summary, including quartiles (Q1, Q3), interquartile range (IQR), minimum–maximum range, median, and 95% confidence interval, providing both central tendency and variability for each meta-model. The transformer not only achieved the best average score but also showed relatively low variability (Balanced accuracy IQR=0.078, Precision IQR=0.098, F1 IQR=0.089), indicating stable performance across different folds and repeats. Figure 4 shows the bootstrap distribution ($n=2,000$) of the final test balanced accuracy for

the proposed meta-transformer. The solid vertical line indicates the mean accuracy, while the dashed line denotes the 95% confidence interval, providing an empirical estimate of performance variability on the held-out test set.

The selected features following the SelectKBest were Cog1, Cog2, Fs2v, T2, avr2, Fs1v, A2, BH2, CohMaxF, and BL2 (Figure 5 and Table 5). Table 5 presents the feature selection stability across all repeated cross-validation runs ($n=3,000$; 50 runs * 6 models * 10 features). Selected count indicates the number of times each feature was included in the Top-K features selected by the ANOVA F-test within a fold, and selection rate (%) represents this frequency as a percentage of all selection events. Higher values indicate features that were consistently selected across different folds and repeats, reflecting their robustness and importance in the meta-learning pipeline.

Figure 6 and Table 6 shows the global SHAP importance values for all mixed meta-inputs (base model probabilities + selected original features). The probability outputs from XGB for class 1 (MCI) and class 2 (HCs) ranked highest, followed by the original feature Cog1. RF probability for class 1 (MCI) and XGB probability for class 0 (dementia) were also among the top contributors. Notably, original features such as Cog1, Cog2, and CohMaxF appeared within the top 10, indicating that the proposed transformer-based meta-classifier did not exclusively depend on base-model outputs. Instead, it effectively combined information from both original features and diverse base-learner predictions. This balanced utilization of heterogeneous inputs likely contributed to its superior performance across all evaluation metrics.

Figure 7 and Table 7 show the global SHAP importance when considering only the original EEG features. Cog1 and Cog2 clearly stand out as the most influential features in the model's predictions. Right after them, CohMaxF and Fs2v follow in importance, while BI2, Bh2, and A2 contribute at a moderate level. The remaining features (T2, avr2, Fs1v) still play a role, but their impact is comparatively smaller. Overall, this ranking highlights that

cognitive-related and coherence-based metrics dominate the model's decision-making when the analysis is restricted to EEG features alone.

Discussion

This study demonstrated the potential of applying a transformer-based meta-classifier within a stacking ensemble framework for EEG-based dementia classification. Unlike conventional meta-models such as RF, LR, SVM, XGB, and MLP, which mainly rely on simple aggregation of base learner outputs, the transformer approach leverages self-attention to dynamically capture interactions between base model predictions and EEG-derived features. Consequently, the proposed meta-transformer achieved the highest balanced accuracy with stable performance across folds. From an interpretability perspective, several noteworthy findings emerged. SHAP analysis revealed that cognitive indicators (Cog1, Cog2) and coherence-related features (e.g., CohMaxF) played a crucial role in the classification process, alongside probability outputs from XGB and RF. This indicates that the transformer meta-classifier does not merely function as a “black-box aggregator” but instead integrates both original EEG features and base model outputs in a balanced and adaptive manner. Nevertheless, some limitations must be acknowledged. The relatively small dataset limits statistical power and requires replication on larger external cohorts. The use of 2-channel wearable EEG imposes constraints compared to high-density EEG or multimodal neuroimaging. The boundary between MCI and dementia is inherently fluid, and thus longitudinal follow-up studies are necessary for clinical translation. Despite these limitations, our findings suggest that combining wearable EEG with transformer-based stacking ensembles represents a promising step toward practical, interpretable tools for early dementia detection.

Conclusion

We confirmed that a transformer meta-classifier can provide improved accuracy, robustness, and interpretability in EEG-based dementia classification. Cognitive measures (Cog1, Cog2) and coherence-derived EEG features emerged as the most influential contributors, while the self-attention mechanism effectively modeled heterogeneous interactions between features and base classifiers. Future work should extend this approach to larger and more diverse datasets, incorporate high-density EEG or multimodal data, and validate its utility in longitudinal clinical studies. Nonetheless, this research highlights the feasibility of integrating practical wearable EEG signals with advanced deep learning techniques to support early dementia screening and diagnosis.

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Figure 1. Proposed framework

Figure 2. Meta-model comparison cross-validation distribution (5 folds * 10 repeated)

Figure 3. Meta-model cross-validation range (min-max) with mean

Figure 4. Final test balanced accuracy (Bootstrap distribution, n=2,000)

Figure 5. Top-10 feature stability (Repeated cross-validation)

Figure 6. Global SHAP importance (Meta-inputs, Mixed)

Figure 7. Global SHAP importance (Original features only)

Table1. Summary of the 72 computed features in the present study

Indices	Description
Cog1	
Cog2	
midF1	
midF2	
rawRMS1	
rawRMS2	
avr1	
avr2	
Fp1	
Fp1v	
Fp1Coh	
Fp2	
Fp2v	
Fp2Coh	
Fs1	
Fs1v	
Fs1Coh	
Fs2	
Fs2v	
Fs2Coh	
Corl	
CohMaxF	
CohMax	
CohAvr	
CohA_T	
CohA_BL	
CohT	
CohA	
CohBL	
CohBH	
A_T1	
A_T2	
T_S1	
T_S2	
T_BL1	
T_BL2	
A_BL1	
A_BL2	
A_BH1	
A_BH2	
T1	
T2	
A1	
A2	
BL1	
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BL2r	
BH1r	
BH2r	
T1o	
T2o	
A1o	
A2o	
BL1o	
BL2o	
BH1o	
BH2o	
T1or	
T2or	
A1or	
A2or	
BL1or	
BL2or	
BH1or	
BH2or	

Table 2. Demographic data of the present study

Variables	Dementia (n=47) a		MCI (n=55) b		HCs (n=43) c		Statistics FDR-corrected p	
	Mean	Std	Mean	Std	Mean	Std		
Age(years)	77.98	7.14	64.38	7.49	59.40	6.09	a>b>c	p<0.001
Education(years)	6.19	4.26	10.29	3.68	12.95	2.95	a<b<c	p<0.001
Sex(m/f)	12/35		26/29		16/27		Chi-squared = 5.13	p=0.077
MMSE	20.47	2.83	26.09	0.87	28.56	0.73	a<b<c	p<0.001
CDR	1.30	0.46	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	a>b>c	p<0.001

Table 3. Statistical results of the present study

Variables	Dementia (n=47) a		MCI (n=55) b		HCs (n=43) c		Statistics FDR-corrected p	
	Mean	Std	Mean	Std	Mean	Std		
Cog1	20.92	2.78	27.15	2.03	28.49	2.00	a<b, a<c	p<0.001
Cog2	20.93	2.84	26.52	2.01	28.47	1.97	a<b<c	p<0.001
T_S1	2.68	1.15	2.04	0.79	2.33	0.82	a>b	p=0.027
T_BI1	2.79	1.31	2.06	0.86	2.28	0.94	a>b	p=0.024

Table 4. Meta-model comparison with cross-validation

Meta-Model	CV-fold	Q1	Q3	IQR	Mean ± Std	Min–Max	Median	95% CI
Balanced accuracy								
Transformer	50	0.657	0.735	0.078	0.694 ± 0.069	0.529–0.905	0.687	0.553–0.818
MLPClassifier		0.579	0.706	0.127	0.638 ± 0.087	0.423–0.857	0.627	0.491–0.794
RandomForest		0.597	0.661	0.065	0.636 ± 0.087	0.423–0.875	0.630	0.489–0.843
LogisticRegression		0.602	0.671	0.069	0.634 ± 0.084	0.423–0.857	0.630	0.470–0.792
SVM		0.595	0.672	0.077	0.632 ± 0.078	0.464–0.857	0.624	0.470–0.780
XGBoost		0.455	0.658	0.203	0.570 ± 0.121	0.407–0.841	0.561	0.407–0.826
Precision								
Transformer		0.643	0.741	0.098	0.687 ± 0.101	0.413–0.933	0.688	0.419–0.845
MLPClassifier		0.597	0.699	0.102	0.646 ± 0.096	0.455–0.909	0.627	0.474–0.844
RandomForest		0.610	0.685	0.075	0.649 ± 0.099	0.455–0.909	0.633	0.475–0.890
LogisticRegression		0.603	0.691	0.088	0.643 ± 0.094	0.455–0.909	0.633	0.462–0.844
SVM		0.595	0.672	0.077	0.640 ± 0.090	0.458–0.909	0.627	0.474–0.844
XGBoost		0.477	0.665	0.188	0.574 ± 0.152	0.271–0.844	0.615	0.302–0.840
F1								
Transformer	0.633	0.723	0.089	0.673 ± 0.085	0.461–0.907	0.674	0.488–0.813	
MLPClassifier	0.580	0.691	0.111	0.633 ± 0.087	0.437–0.857	0.622	0.481–0.791	
RandomForest	0.591	0.661	0.070	0.632 ± 0.085	0.437–0.864	0.624	0.482–0.842	
LogisticRegression	0.590	0.661	0.071	0.629 ± 0.083	0.437–0.857	0.625	0.465–0.787	
SVM	0.591	0.667	0.076	0.626 ± 0.078	0.461–0.857	0.615	0.475–0.768	
XGBoost	0.416	0.640	0.224	0.538 ± 0.151	0.290–0.833	0.555	0.308–0.821	

Table 5. Frequency of Top-10 feature selection (stability analysis)

Features	Selected count	Selection rate(%)
Cog1	300	10
Cog2	300	10
Fs2v	294	9.8
T2	294	9.8
avr2	264	8.8
Fs1v	228	7.6
A2	210	7
BH2	180	6
CohMaxF	168	5.6
BL2	162	5.4

Table 6. Meta-inputs SHAP importance with mixed

Meta-features	Mean-SHAP
XGB_prob_class1	0.866
XGB_prob_class2	0.590
Cog1	0.548
RF_prob_class1	0.469
XGB_prob_class0	0.465
Cog2	0.362
RF_prob_class2	0.264
RF_prob_class0	0.188
SVM_prob_class0	0.182
CohMaxF	0.157

Table 7. Meta-inputs SHAP importance with original features

Meta-features	Mean-SHAP
Cog1	0.548
Cog2	0.362
CohMaxF	0.157
Fs2v	0.146
Bl2	0.115
Bh2	0.085
A2	0.084
T2	0.073
avr2	0.068
Fs1v	0.038

